

Ground Water Analysis in Rahuri Tehsil of Ahmednagar District, M.S., India.

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Abstract:

Rainfall is the most important source of water to the river and this rainfall is considered important for underground water supply. However, due to these man-made and natural causes, the quality of drinking water is decreasing to a large extent, so it is necessary to study the drinking water or various water sources. The quality of ground water in the study area is not same at different sampling stations. The main reason behind this variation may be the variation in geographical conditions and anthropogenic activities. The present study may prove to be of some help in understanding the quality of ground water resources of the study area.

Keywords: Ground water, Quality, Characteristics, Physico-chemical, Parameters.

Introduction:

Today, the groundwater contamination is widely taking place because of either natural reasons or human actions. Thus, it requires a regular monitoring of water quality to device ways and means to maintain it. The ground water important sources of water being use for irrigation in the Rahuri tehsil where, sugarcane is the main cash crop. The practice of over irrigation, use of pesticides, weedicides, chemical fertilizers and discharge of industrial effluent may affect the groundwater quality^[6]. Thus, this communication describes a systematic study on Physico-chemical characteristics of ground water from downstream area of Pravara River in Rahuri tehsil of Ahmednagar district in Maharashtra, India. Water is vital natural resource, supporting life and environment that we have constantly supposed to be available in profusion and gift of nature (Kjellen, M., et al. 2000). It has been severely affect by rapid economic development and intensified human activities. (Nickson et al. 2005). The utilization of ground water for domestic, industrial and irrigation purpose has been constantly increasing particularly, where perennial surface water sources are scarce. (Mathussalam A. et. al. 2004). The most important source of water is rainfall which increases the level of wells. Geology is an important factor in water level^[7,8]. There are natural and man-made causes of water pollution, of which man-made causes are the most dangerous. Agriculture is considered an important factor for well water pollution as large

quantities of chemical fertilizers and sprays are used for agriculture which affects water quality^[4,5]. There are two types of resource, one is natural resource and other is man-made resource. Natural resource includes various elements such as soil, water, vegetation etc. while human resource includes human quality, skill, and knowledge^[14,15]. As a result, human beings have made their own and economic progress on the strength of their intellect, but we have seen an increase in pollution^[16,17,19].

Study Area:

Rahuri tehsil is centrally located in the scarcity zone of Ahmednagar district in Maharashtra. Geographically, it lies between 19° 15' 00" N to 19° 34' 00" N latitude and 74° 23' 30" E to 74° 50' 00" E longitude and is divided into the basins of river Mula and Pravara. Distribution of rainfall in the tehsil is uneven where and average rainfall about 520 mm. The tehsil receives its most of the rain during southwest monsoon season. Here, the maximum temperature ranges from 28°C to 41°C and sometimes raises up to 45°C in summer season. Minimum temperatures range between 7°C to 22°C while coolest climatic conditions prevail in winter. The total geographical area of the tehsil is about 92,867 hectares. Out of which 29,045 hectares area (31.28%) is under irrigation. The tehsil comprises of 95 villages and 2 urban centers viz. Rahuri and Deolali-Pravara. Canal, dug wells, and bore wells are the important modes of irrigation being use in the tehsil.

Map no 01: Location Map

Objectives:

The main objectives of the present study is to study the Ground Water Analysis in Rahuri Tehsil. they calculated pH, Electrical Conductivity (EC) and Temperature were measurement in site. Carbonate (CO_3^{2-}), Bicarbonate (HCO_3^-), Chloride (Cl^-), Magnesium (Mg^{++}), Calcium (Ca^{++}), sodium (Na^+) and Potassium (K^+)

Data Sources And Methodology:

Primary and secondary data has been used for this research paper. Eleven villages have been selected mainly for fieldwork and sampling collection in the primary information and samples have been taken from one well in these 11 villages. These experiments have been checked in the laboratory. Also the information in the secondary data form is collected from the research article and reference book. Also cartography met

hods are used to convert numerical information into qualitative information in which mainly bar graph are drawn. GIS software has also been used to create the maps and GPS has been used to capture the sampling location. And using statistical methods of Liner regression for water Temp, ph. and Mg^{++} .

Material and Methods:

Ground water samples were collect from randomly selected eleven dug wells in Rahuri tehsil, each from the area of a separate village, located in downstream area of river Pravara (Map 2). Water samples were collected from eleven villages according to eleven villages Ambi, Aradgaon, Chinchvihire, Jogeshwari-Aakhada, Khudsargaon, Manori, Musalwadi, Rahuri, Tambhere, Tilapur, Valan. The water collection is for the period June 2022.

Map: 1. Sampling Villages

Samples collected during monsoon, 2022, in sterilized plastic bottles were brought to the laboratory and the studied Physico-chemical parameters. Unstable parameters viz. pH, Electrical Conductivity (EC) and Temperature were measurement in site. Carbonate (CO_3^{--}), Bicarbonate (HCO_3^-), Chloride (Cl^-), Magnesium (Mg^{++}), Calcium (Ca^{++}), sodium (Na^+) and Potassium (K^+) were analyzed by applying standard methods. Further, the basic statistical analysis was carried out for different physico-chemical parameters.

Results and Discussion:

The temperature of ground water samples collected from different wells is found in a range of 28.2^0 C and 31.9^0 C. The maximum temperature was observe at Aradgaon, while minimum temperature was record at Musalwadi. The pH values were varies from 7.00 to 7.6, indicating alkaline nature of ground water in the study area. The maximum pH

was observed at Aradgaon, Manori, Musalwadi and Tilapur while, the minimum of it was recorded at Chinchvihire and Tambhere. The electrical conductivity was found between 1.2 and 11.7 mm. The maximum value of it was recorded at Chinchvihire and the minimum at Aradgaon. It is noteworthy that, not a single site of sampling has reported the presence of carbonate. The values of bicarbonate were observed between 1.6 and 6.5 meq/lit. The maximum value was recorded at Manori and the minimum was recorded at Jogeshwari Aakhada and Rahuri. The values of chloride were found in the range of 3.2 and 47.6 meq/lit. The maximum value was recorded at Chinchvihire while the minimum of it was found at Jogeshwari Aakhada. One of the most important causes of water quality degradation in rural areas is water quality degradation due to chemical fertilizers and sprays used in agriculture.

Table: 1 Result of Ground Water Analyses

Sr. No.	Name of Site	Temp	pH	EC	CO_3^{--}	HCO_3^-	Cl^-	Ca^{++}	Mg^{++}	K^+	Na^+
1	Ambi	30.5	7.1	2.2	00	5.1	3.1	4.4	8.4	0.0387	1.14
2	Aradgaon	30.9	7.5	1.2	00	2.2	5.0	24.8	11.2	0.0151	3.2
3	Chinchvihire	28.6	7.2	11.0	00	2.2	45.1	19.2	68.8	0.0194	9.29
4	Jogeshwari-Aakhada	31.0	7.2	2.0	00	1.8	3.1	14.4	11.2	0.022	4.61
5	Khudsargaon	21.3	7.4	5.7	00	6.2	13.0	14.4	38.8	0.0376	6.42
6	Manori	33.5	7.1	1.2	00	6.5	10.4	14.0	26.0	0.0167	14.1
7	Musalwadi	28.2	7.7	2.1	00	2.2	31.8	1.6	10.0	0.0140	4.33
8	Rahuri	29.6	7.2	10.5	00	1.1	7.0	8.0	110.0	0.026	14.27
9	Tambhere	29.6	7.6	4.4	00	2.2	20.0	4.4	16.0	0.071	7.51
10	Tilapur	32.6	7.2	1.1	00	2.1	21.6	2.4	60.2	0.351	0.21
11	Valan	32.6	7.1	8.0	00	2.0	16.8	12.8	63.2	0.0296	7.01

Notes: All parameters are expressed in meq/lit except temp., pH and EC (mmhos).

The calcium values were in a range of 1.6 (Musalwadi) and 24.8 meq/lit (Aaradgaon). The values of magnesium were recorded between 8.4 and 110 meq/lit. At Ambi and Rahuri respectively. The Potassium values were in the range of 0.0140 and 0.351 meq/lit. The maximum value was recorded at Tilapur while, minimum was found at Musalwadi. The range of Sodium was observed from 0.21 to 14.27 meq/lit at Tilapur and Rahuri respectively (Table 1). The village wise concentration of chemical parameters is depicted in Figure 1. The statistical analysis has been carried out for different parameters of ground water and the results are depicted in table 1, which shows the values of minimum, maximum, range, and mean, Standard Deviation, Standard Error and Coefficient of Variation for all the obtained parameters. The suitability of ground water for irrigation depends on the amount of salts present in it. High or little amount of salts present in the water to be used for irrigation thus, decide the water quality. The

concentrations of these salts and their ratios were obtained by using water quality indices viz. Sodium Absorption Ratio (SAR), Residual Sodium Carbonate (RSC), Kelly's Ratio (KR) and Soluble Sodium Percentage (SSP).. It is clear from, the ground water quality is moderately safe (USDA, 1954) for irrigating the crops. The most important source of water pollution is water from factories and domestic women. Agriculture is also responsible for various arrests. Water pollution is not caused by natural causes but man-made causes are considered to be the most important hazards. There will be shortage of drinking water. In the study session the pH is the highest so in short the pH of the water in each village is higher today. This means that there is more agriculture in that place. The important reason for this is that chemical fertilizers are being used on a large scale in these areas, if this amount increases, it will create a large health hazard in the future. The most important reason why Rahuri cities show the highest level of water pollution is that the sewage water from the entire Rahuri city is discharged in this area, which results in a large amount of water

pollution. In short, there is a need for a large number of water filters for Rahuri Tehsil. Areas with low levels of calcium pose a significant risk to human health. Because calcium strengthens a person's

bones, this means that those areas can develop a greater number of bone health problems in the future.

Graph no 02: Graphical Presentation Of Chemical Parameters.

Graph no 02: Liner Regression between water temperature and Ph

Liner regression between water Tem and Ph is 0.1834 it is positive relation

Graph no 03: Liner regression between water Tem and Mg++

Liner regression between water Tem and Mg++ it is Negative Relation

In order to study the correlation of water in this field, there is a positive relationship between

temperature and salinity, that is, in short, there is a relationship between salinity and water temperature, but in short, these two factors affect each other, at the same time, there is a negative relationship

between temperature and magnesium, in short, these two factors do not affect each other.

Conclusion:

One of the most important causes of water quality degradation in rural areas is water quality degradation due to chemical fertilizers and sprays used in agriculture. For this, the use of organic fertilizers is very necessary otherwise the quality of water in rural areas will be faced in the coming years. In order to study the correlation of water in this field, there is a positive relationship between temperature and salinity, that is, in short, there is a relationship between salinity and water temperature, but in short, these two factors affect each other, at the same time, there is a negative relationship between temperature and magnesium, in short, these two factors do not affect each other.

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